

Stimulator of interferon genes (STING)-activating nanoparticles can be employed as a tool for controlled immune activation

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Abstract- Advances in materials and chemistry have helped stimulator of interferon genes (STING) agonists deliver nanomedicine, and drug delivery scientists have generated a spate of STING-activating nanocarriers capable of bypassing biological barriers for targeted innate and adaptive immune activation. Using STING-activating nanoparticles in antiviral vaccination has yielded several promising results in preclinical studies, and the strong antiviral humoral and cellular immunity elicited by these particulate adjuvants against HIV, influenza, and coronaviruses justifies the continued development of the platforms against the global infectious threat. STING-activating nanoparticles can be employed in virology and immunology research as a tool for controlled immune activation, as many processes underpinning STING-mediated immunological potency in viral infections are yet unclear. Because many of the nanoparticle platforms used to deliver STING agonists may also be utilized with various molecular adjuvants, these systems may be utilized to examine how diverse innate immune signals impact adaptive immunity production. Combinatorial nanoparticles mixing STING agonists with other molecular adjuvants may further increase antiviral protectivity by synergistically increasing immunological potential. Despite the promise of nanoparticulate vaccines, these synthetic nanoparticles are strikingly absent from COVID-19 vaccine research worldwide talks. Many elements, such as formulation safety, manufacturing scalability, storage, and deployment logistics, must be considered to achieve the enormous potential of the nanoparticulate STING agonists. Reduced synthetic methods and formulation lyophilization are important factors in platform designs to make antiviral vaccines accessible and affordable to poor nations. Nevertheless, the platform's great efficiency and wide use provide promise advances in both fundamental and translational research, opening the way to a deeper knowledge of viral containment and superior approaches.

I. INTRODUCTION

The public and scientific communities are being reminded of the critical need to create effective and widely neutralizing antiviral vaccines as a result of recent emergent and re-emerging viral diseases. The ongoing COVID-19 pandemic has attracted unprecedented public attention, private and public funding, and global research and commercial efforts for vaccine research, with both traditional (subunit antigens and inactivated viruses) and emerging (DNA, mRNA, and vectored vaccines) vaccine platforms being developed and rolled out for clinical trials at breakneck speed. Simultaneously, new advancements in nanoparticle and nanomaterial-based vaccination research provide synthetically flexible tools for improved control of immune activation, providing safer and more effective answers to several decade-long issues in vaccine development. In light of the exciting findings of STING in the last decade, a rising body of research has concentrated on nanomedical delivery of stimulator of interferon genes (STING) agonists for immunotherapy and vaccine research, with nanocarriers having been used for a range of molecular adjuvants (1). STING, a conserved intracellular pattern recognition receptor, is gaining increasing scientific interest as a key player in innate immune sensing of foreign pathogens (2), and its signaling pathway is unique in registering nucleic acid insignia from foreign pathogens, and it plays an important role in antiviral defense. When a virus infects a cell, the cytoplasmic enzyme cyclic GMP-AMP synthetase (cGAS) recognizes viral DNA and produces the secondary messenger 2',3'-cyclic GMP-AMP (cGAMP), which activates STING and initiates an inflammation-driven immune response (3). The STING signaling pathway has been shown to play an important role in antiviral defense against a variety of DNA and RNA viruses, including West Nile virus (4–6), influenza (7), human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) (8), severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV) (9), and Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV) (10). (MERS-CoV). Type-I interferon, the major cytokine produced in response to STING signaling, also serves as a signaling link between innate and adaptive immunity. Nanoparticulate STING agonists provide the possibility of safely producing more efficient immune responses that rival those seen after live infections in the context of nanoparticle-based vaccinations. We present an overview of DNA sensing via the cGAS–STING pathway in this paper, as well as the rising popularity of nanoparticulate STING agonists and their use in vaccine development. The difficulties of encapsulating STING agonists and the development of different techniques and biomaterials for boosting STING activation are

highlighted. We also present experiments that illustrate the applicability of STING-activation based nanovaccines in disease models, including influenza, HIV, and coronaviruses, in light of the increased interest in antiviral vaccines in the wake of the SARS-CoV2 pandemic.

II. INNATE AND ADAPTIVE IMMUNITY ARE BOTH INFLUENCED BY STING SIGNALING.

The STING pathway was found as part of the host's cellular defense against pathogens, which involves the recognition of foreign nucleic acids and the synthesis of cyclic dinucleotides (CDNs) as secondary messengers (3,10). Because of their potential to bind and activate the STING receptor in antigen presenting cells, endogenously generated or externally provided CDNs have been widely used in antibacterial and antiviral vaccines (11,12). STING activates transcription factors NF- κ B and IRF3, which translocate into the nucleus and initiate the production of proinflammatory cytokines and chemokines such as IFN- γ (13–17). IFN- γ stimulates the IFNAR1 and IFNAR2 heterodimeric receptor complex, which is found on the surface of many different types of cells, including immune cells. JAK–STAT signaling transduces the receptor dimer complex and stimulates the expression of numerous interferon-stimulated genes, the protein products of which impede viral replication, assembly, and release (18). STING signaling is intimately linked to the enhancement of adaptive immune response, since IFN- γ acts as a danger associated molecular pattern (DAMP) that signals a state of pathogenic infection to the immune system by priming DCs for T-cell activation (19). It aids the clonal selection of viral antigen-specific effector cytotoxic T lymphocytes (CTLs) in secondary lymphoid tissues and their trafficking to inflammatory areas (20). Conventional type 1 dendritic cells (cDC1) interact and begin antigen presentation and priming of CD4⁺ T cells in secondary lymph nodes via CD40L–CD40 costimulatory binding, which results in the production of IL-12 and IL-15. Dendritic cells (DCs) activated by CD40 exhibit increased amounts of CD80 and CD86, which help CD8⁺ T cells differentiate into effector and memory CTLs (21). Activated CD4⁺ T cells also play a role in priming B cells to proliferate and differentiate into memory effector B cells that produce virus-neutralizing antibodies with high affinity (22). Furthermore, type-I IFN can operate as a lymphocyte activation signal, promoting the proliferation of CD4 and CD8 T cells directly. In vaccine development, inducing type-I IFN responses by activating STING signaling can be extremely beneficial to the establishment of antiviral humoral and cellular immunity. STING agonists are formed into nanoplateforms and coupled with viral antigens to induce the formation of CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells as well as antibody-secreting plasma cells, resulting in efficient antiviral vaccines.

The use of STING agonists in vaccines opens up the possibility of molecular adjuvants in inflammation-based priming of antiviral immunity that mimics natural host responses, and the primary appeal of using nanoparticulate STING agonists for antiviral vaccination is their ability to expand adaptive immune responses to recombinant protein antigens. In fact, the impact of STING agonists on innate and adaptive immune responses has been well-documented in cancer immunotherapy research, as scientists seek to use these two arms of the immune system to improve tumor elimination. DNA fragments from dying tumor cells (23) and exogenously given STING agonists (24) have been shown to boost tumor-resident DC activation and adaptive immune responses to tumor antigens.

STING agonists have been shown to have a direct effect on innate immunity by inducing a wide range of inflammatory responses, including the secretion of pro-inflammatory molecules and cytokines (25), activation of NK cells (27), and recruitment of phagocytic macrophages into the tumor microenvironment (28). Many STING activating nanoparticles have been produced by diverse synthetic processes in the domains of cancer immunotherapy and antiviral vaccine research with the goal of improving STING-mediated immune activation.

III. STING-ACTIVATING NANOPARTICLES SYNTHESIS TECHNIQUES

CDN distribution efficiency is often low because STING proteins are situated in the intracellular domain, and CDNs are very polar and hydrophilic. Therefore, substantial dosages of the molecules are commonly required to elicit a powerful immune response. Furthermore, the tendency of STING agonists to hydrolyze in the presence of DNase necessitates the use of a dependable delivery vehicle. Because CDNs are anionic, cationic nanocarriers have been widely used to improve CDN delivery. Cationic platforms, such as silica nanoparticles, create sufficient surface charge by amine modification to interact electrostatically with c-di-GMP or bis-(3'-5')-cyclic dimeric guanosine monophosphate (29). Park et al. (30) produced a biodegradable form of mesoporous silica nanoparticles to improve STING agonist delivery for cancer immunotherapy. Koshy et al. used cationic lipid 1,2-Dioleoyl-3-trimethylammoniumpropane (DOTAP)/cholesterol liposomes to encapsulate cGAMP, demonstrating the concept of electrostatic interaction in liposomal carriers. The liposomes were made using a conventional thin film rehydration process, freeze thawing, and membrane extrusion with a surface modification of 5 and 10 mol percent. 1,2-distearoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine-N (methoxy (polyethylene glycol)-2000), (DSPE-PEG (2000)) for stability (31). Wilson et al. used a hydrophobic poly-(beta-amino esters) with a disulfide backbone to activate STING at low CDN concentrations by enhancing delivery efficiency to human monocytes (32). The biodegradable poly-(beta-amino esters) polymers' disulfide backbone is specially intended to promote fast intracellular breakdown, reducing the cytotoxic problems frequently associated with cationic carriers.

The hydrophilic STING agonists are encapsulated in the second group of STING-activating nanoparticles, which use core–shell architectures. Repeated freeze–thaw cycles or rehydration of lipid films with extremely concentrated CDN solution have been used to establish direct CDN encapsulation in noncationic liposomes (36,37). However, because a considerable number of the hydrophilic molecules are likely to partition into the outer aqueous phase, such a method is typically thought to have low or inconsistent encapsulation effectiveness. Shae et al. designed pH-responsive polymersomes consisting of amphiphilic diblock copolymer chains with an aqueous core to improve CDN encapsulation and delivery (38). The membrane-destabilizing activity of the polymer facilitates intracellular transport and endosomal escape of cGAMP. The

technique has also been shown to be susceptible to co-encapsulation of peptides and STING agonists for anticancer vaccination (39). Junkins et al. used a coaxial electrohydrodynamic spraying approach using cGAMP dissolved in water and Ace-DEX dissolved in an ethyl acetate/butanol/ethanol co-solvent to make acid-sensitive acetylated dextran (Ace-DEX) polymeric microparticles devoid of any cationic component. The microparticles were collected on a phosphatidylcholine-coated charged plate, and they improved STING agonist lymphatic delivery to induce a robust type-I interferon response (40). Chattopadhyay et al. produced polymeric nanoshells with a low-viscosity, carboxyl-terminated PLGA utilizing a double emulsion solvent evaporation process to make noncationic nanoparticulate STING agonists with regulated CDN encapsulation and release (34). Hollow polymeric nanoparticles with a shell thickness as low as 10 nm and a large inner aqueous core were formed using an improved polymer mix and emulsion methodology for high encapsulation of hydrophilic cGAMP and other adjuvants (41). Because of the hydrolytic kinetics of the PLGA polymer, the compositionally simple nanoshells are intrinsically pH-responsive, allowing for safe and regulated delivery of STING agonists. Precipitation of calcium and phosphate salts is another method for making CDN-encapsulated nanoparticles. It has been demonstrated that CDNs can be loaded inside the resulting calcium phosphate nanoparticles at a high efficiency for pH-sensitive release using a two-step water-in-oil reverse microemulsion method followed by lipid coating, resulting in enhanced immune stimulation for anticancer treatment (42).

In addition to delivering STING agonists, nanoparticles containing STING activating compounds that are not included in CDNs are another type of STING-activating nanocarrier. Luo et al. presented a minimalist nanovaccine containing cancer antigen OVA combined with micellar nanoparticles made from copolymerized PEG-b and STING activating polymer PC7A in a groundbreaking work (PEG-b-PC7A). The researchers looked at a collection of copolymers containing tertiary amines with either linear or cyclic side chains. The strongest CTL response was seen in poly (ethylpropylamino) ethyl methacrylate (PEPA) NPs containing the cyclic seven-membered ring of PC7A, owing to STING activation by the cyclic polymer architecture (43). The cGAMP-loaded ultra-pH-sensitive nanoparticles were then used to boost STING activation for antiviral applications (35).

Miao et al. used an isocyanide-mediated one-step three-component reaction (3-CR) to screen a library of 1080 lipids and identify structure–function connections toward the synthesis of STING-activatable cyclic lipids, using a similar screening technique. For intracellular mRNA delivery, these lipids were synthesized into nanoparticles (LNPs). The researchers discovered a number of lipid compositions that improve mediated STING activation, allowing for the development of mRNA-based vaccines with improved CTL responses (33).

In addition to the three types of STING-activating nanoparticles discussed above, new design concepts for mediating STING activation are being developed. Nanoparticles coated with cytosine-rich i-motif DNA, for example, have been created for direct cyclic-di-GMP loading through C: G base pairing. pH-sensitive release of cyclic-di-GMP for immune activation is enabled by the unique feature of i-motif DNA in undergoing conformational change at acidic pH (44).

He et al., who generated recombinant STING proteins capable of complexing with 2' cyclic GMP-AMP for intracellular delivery, presented a more creative design for STING agonist administration. The bioinspired design also has the added benefit of initiating STING signaling in STING-deficient cells, potentially broadening the scope of STING-activating complexes' applicability. In addition, due to the difficulties of synthesizing CDNs in delivery vehicles, especially when combined with other therapeutic agents. Several research (45,46) have chosen to use double-stranded DNA to activate cGAS in the cGAS-STING signaling pathway. In addition, DMXAA (5,6-dimethylxantheone-4-acetic acid), a hydrophobic version of the STING agonist, has been integrated into the hydrophobic core of solid nanoparticles for anticancer chemo-immunotherapy (47). This abundance of synthetic techniques for STING-activating nanoparticle production reflects drug delivery experts' increasing interest in the inner workings of innate immune activation, and it provides a growing arsenal for STING-signaling-based immunotherapy and vaccine development.

IV. ANTIVIRAL IMMUNIZATION WITH STING-ACTIVATING NANOPARTICLES

While the majority of STING-activating nanoparticles have been used in cancer immunotherapy and vaccination, multiple studies have indicated that these immune-stimulating nanoparticles can improve antiviral vaccination efforts and resolve long-standing issues that have hampered vaccine effectiveness. HIV, influenza, and coronaviruses, in particular, are still major public health concerns that drive ongoing research into new vaccine formulations. The findings presented in this section emphasize the use of STING-activating nanoparticles in the development of vaccines against various pathogenic diseases.

Despite over 30 years of study, no anti-HIV vaccine has been authorized, exemplifying the obstacles and challenges that might be encountered in vaccine development. HIV was discovered to cause AIDS in 1984, a disease in which the number of CD4⁺ T-cells decreases with time, resulting in impaired cell-based immunity (48). By the end of 2018, WHO projects that 37.9 million people will be living with HIV, with 1.7 million new infections and 0.77 million deaths a year. Although therapies like combination antiretroviral therapy make illness symptoms bearable, long-term use raises concerns about safety and medication resistance (49,50).

The existence of several viral subtypes and the fast evolution of the RNA virus hamper vaccine development against HIV, making antigen target selection challenging (51–54). The recent identification of broadly neutralizing epitopes that are weakly immunogenic gives reason for optimism, and immunologic adjuvants, such as STING-activating nanoparticles, are one of the numerous techniques being investigated to

encourage the formation of broadly neutralizing antibodies.

Hanson et al. demonstrated two liposome-based HIV vaccines with excellent lymphatic distribution of STING agonist cyclic-di-GMP (cdGMP) and HIV antigen to improve anti-HIV immunization. CDGMP is inserted into liposomes coupled with monophosphoryl lipid-A (MPLA) and membrane-proximal external region (MPER) peptides that are covalently linked to the lipid membrane in one formulation. MPER's liposomal delivery allows for interaction with lipid micelles, which gives the peptide a defined helical form and increases its immunogenicity. The liposomal vaccination allows for better priming of germinal center B cell populations as well as the generation of high neutralizing antibody titers (36). The authors studied the effects of lymph node targeting of the adjuvant by liposomal HIV gp41 peptide antigen and cdGMP in the second formulation. The researchers discovered that nanoparticles were retained effectively in the draining lymph nodes (dLN), resulting in localized type-I IFN production. In the dLNs, it resulted in the proliferation of antigen-specific CD4⁺ T cells as well as germinal center B cells (37). Aroh et al. used cGAMP-loaded PC7A nanoparticles to produce a wide and prolonged antiretroviral innate immune response driven by type-I IFN upregulation as an alternative to using STING-activating nanoparticles for anti-HIV therapy. The nanoparticles limit viral replication in HIV⁺ patients' PBMCs for a long time (35). These findings suggest that STING-activating nanoparticles can enhance HIV management by increasing innate and adaptive immunity.

Influenza viruses are another seasonal public health issue, presenting symptoms ranging from moderate to severe diseases, as well as significant mortality in individuals 65 and older. The flu causes 3.5 million severe illnesses and almost 400,000 fatalities worldwide each year (58). Current vaccine formulations are restricted in their capacity to respond to the fast antigenic drift of the immunodominant epitopes in the viral hemagglutinin (HA) and neuraminidase (NA) proteins, despite the fact that influenza vaccinations are routinely delivered to restrict the illness. Furthermore, current influenza vaccines have a short shelf life, with antibody titers dropping within a year (59), needing yearly reformulation and booster immunization. STING agonists have been used to increase vaccine protection in continuing efforts to develop a broadly neutralizing influenza vaccine (60,61).

Junkins et al. demonstrated that an acid-sensitive acetylated dextran microparticle (Ace-DEX MP) may be utilized to deliver cGAMP, resulting in a 1000-fold increase in type-I interferon responses *in vitro* and a 50-fold increase *in vivo*, with the goal of increasing cellular immunity to influenza vaccination. When HA was combined with the microparticle, anti-influenza neutralizing antibody titers were substantially higher than when antigens were combined with soluble cGAMP. The scientists also noticed a pattern of Th1-related responses, such as memory T cell growth and germinal center B cell proliferation. Mice inoculated with HA and Ace-DEX cGAMP MPs were resistant to a deadly influenza infection seven months later at levels up to 100 times lower than previously reported soluble CDNs (40).

Chen et al. improved the Ace-DEX MP platform for customizable particle degradation and cGAMP release in subsequent work (62). The authors demonstrated that a sustained STING agonist release profile from the MPs resulted in greater antibody production, cellular immunity, and antiviral protectivity in mice using a weakly immunogenic antigen derived from the highly conserved ectodomain of matrix protein 2 (M2e) across many influenza subtypes. The study emphasizes the importance of spatiotemporal control between innate immune signaling and antigen presentation for optimal vaccination, echoing many findings in immunology research that emphasize the importance of spatiotemporal control between innate immune signaling and antigen presentation (63,64).

Wang et al. employed cGAMP-containing liposomes in combination with a clinically licensed inactivated viral vaccine to imitate heterosubtypic influenza immunity in another work that uses a nanoparticulate STING agonist for universal influenza vaccination. The liposomes were decorated with lipid components from pulmonary surfactant (PS), a phospholipoprotein generated by alveolar epithelial cells (AEC) and recognized by lung-resident alveolar macrophages, to simulate the surface chemistry of the lung. The authors show that PS-cGAMP was rapidly taken up by alveolar macrophages in mice after intranasal treatment, resulting in transitory, localized activation of innate immunity. The innate myeloid cells subsequently cross-prime CD8⁺ T cells effectively, inducing strong protection against numerous influenza strains (56). The vaccine formulation was shown to protect mice against influenza within two days of inoculation, and the scientists stated that CD8 T cell-mediated immunity, rather than innate immunological responses, was responsible for this early protection. This early protection was also unique to the PS-cGAMP-adjuvanted vaccine, as vaccines made with cholera toxin and poly (I: C) exhibited no survival advantage under identical circumstances. The findings suggest that STING-activating nanoparticles may boost immunity in ways that conventional adjuvant formulations can't, providing a compelling strategy for boosting mucosal immunity against respiratory infections.

COVID-19 is a serious respiratory illness caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 that has almost 9 million confirmed cases and over 460,000 fatalities as of June 22, 2020. (SARS-CoV-2). Antiviral vaccinations are urgently needed to stop the disease's spread, and various vaccine formulations are entering and proceeding through clinical trials at a breakneck pace. Many issues and concerns from earlier vaccination experiences against similar coronaviruses (i.e., SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV (middle east respiratory syndrome coronavirus)) remain unresolved despite hope and ambitions for the COVID-19 vaccine development landscape (65). Prior coronavirus vaccine development has been hampered by two possible safety concerns: antibody-dependent enhancement (ADE) and cellular immunopathology (66).

The implications of these issues have pushed vaccine designers to use reductionist antigens with neutralizing epitopes, as well as

immunological adjuvants that can boost cellular immunity and Th1 responses. In particular, a recent study on convalescent COVID-19 patients found that the development of a significant CD4+ and CD8+ T-cell response against SARS-CoV-2 spike receptor binding domain (RBD) was significantly correlated with a high neutralizing titer of antibodies against RBD (68), indicating that cellular immunity as well as anti-RBD antibodies are good correlates of protective immunity. It's worth noting that a recent study found that the protein products of the SARS-CoV-2 genome's ORF3b gene can inhibit type I IFN activity during infection (69), raising the possibility that such interference might compromise adaptive immunity in infected individuals. Furthermore, it's unclear if ongoing coronavirus alterations may jeopardize the efficacy of vaccine candidates now under development. While the judgment is still out on what makes an efficient COVID-19 coronavirus vaccine, the inclusion of the nanoparticulate STING agonist into anti-coronavirus vaccine preparations has shown encouraging results that merit further exploration (57).

Lin et al. created a hollow polymeric nanoparticle loaded with STING agonist cdGMP and coated with recombinant RBD antigens as a vaccination candidate for MERS-CoV, drawing inspiration from the appearance and characteristics of coronaviruses. Tunable STING agonist loading, multivalent surface RBD presentation, and pH-responsive STING agonist release are all aspects of the viromimetic vaccine formulation. In vaccinated mice, the stable nanoparticle structures allow delivery of STING agonist and RBD antigens to the draining lymph node and antigen presenting cells, evoking robust and long-lasting neutralizing antibody titers with a balanced Th1/Th2 profile and antigen-specific T cell responses. The nanoparticle vaccination provided 100 percent protection against a deadly challenge from MERS-CoV in human DPP4 transgenic mice (57), and no immunopathology was found after the viral challenge. The study also shows that the nanoparticle formulation causes no reactogenic reactivity and can be stored for a long time, both of which are important concerns for clinical translation. Despite the fact that MERS-CoV varies from SARS-CoV2 in epidemiology and several constitutive proteins, the current SARS-CoV2 vaccine design paradigm shares many antigen selection and immune potentiation criteria with SARS-CoV2 (68,70). As a result, it's possible that including STING-activating nanoparticles into COVID-19 research efforts might speed up and improve the virus's control by potentiating the intended immune response.

V. CONCLUSION

Materials and chemistry advancements have aided nanomedicinal delivery of STING agonists, and drug delivery experts have produced a slew of STING-activating nanocarriers capable of penetrating biological barriers for targeted innate and adaptive immune activation. The use of STING-activating nanoparticles in antiviral vaccination has yielded a number of promising results in preclinical studies, and the strong antiviral humoral and cellular immunity elicited by these particulate adjuvants against HIV, influenza, and coronaviruses justifies the platforms' continued development against the global infectious threat. STING-activating nanoparticles can be used as a tool for regulated immune activation in virology and immunology research because many processes behind STING-mediated immune potentiation in viral infections are yet unknown. Because many of the nanoparticle platforms used to deliver STING agonists may also be used with other molecular adjuvants, these systems might be used to investigate how varied innate immune signals modulate the formation of adaptive immunity. Combinatorial nanoparticles that mix STING agonists with other molecular adjuvants may further improve antiviral protectivity by enhancing immune potentiation synergistically. Despite the promise of nanoparticulate vaccinations, these synthetic nanoparticles are conspicuously absent from discussions of the COVID-19 vaccine research landscape throughout the world. Many variables, such as formulation safety, manufacturing scalability, storage, and deployment logistics, must be considered in order to achieve the huge potential of nanoparticulate STING agonists. Reduced synthetic processes and lyophilizability of formulations are significant aspects of platform designs for making antiviral vaccines accessible and inexpensive for impoverished nations. Nonetheless, the platform's high effectiveness and broad use offer promising advancements in both basic and translational research, opening the door for a deeper understanding of viral containment and enhanced methods.

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